
Impact of Sugar Factory on Agriculture Development in Karad Tahsil

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063382

Abstract:

Sugar factories contribute significantly to the rural economy by creating employment opportunities and supporting allied industries such as transportation, machinery, and bio-product manufacturing. The introduction of cooperative sugar factories in particular has empowered farmers, giving them greater control over pricing and profits while promoting a sense of collective ownership. However, the increased focus on sugarcane cultivation has also raised concerns regarding soil degradation, water usage, and crop diversity.

This study aims to explore the multifaceted impact of sugar factories on agricultural development in Karad Tahsil, highlighting their role in improving rural livelihoods while addressing the challenges posed to sustainable agricultural practices.

Keywords: *Sugar Factories, Agriculture Development, Karad and Satara.*

Introduction:

Agriculture is the backbone of rural economies, and in regions like Karad Tahsil, it plays a vital role in shaping the livelihood of farmers and the overall development of the area. One significant factor that has contributed to agricultural growth and rural transformation in this region is the establishment of sugar factories. Sugarcane cultivation, being a primary crop in Karad, has driven the establishment of sugar factories, which, in turn, have had a profound impact on the local agricultural landscape.

The sugar industry in Karad Tahsil acts as a key catalyst for agricultural development by providing a stable market for sugarcane farmers, ensuring financial security, and encouraging modern farming practices. Farmers in the region have embraced sugarcane cultivation due to its high profitability compared to traditional crops. This has led to an increased demand for fertilizers, irrigation facilities, and

mechanized farming tools, further modernizing the agricultural sector.

Moreover, sugar factories contribute significantly to the rural economy by creating employment opportunities and supporting allied industries such as transportation, machinery, and bio-product manufacturing. The introduction of cooperative sugar factories in particular has empowered farmers, giving them greater control over pricing and profits while promoting a sense of collective ownership. However, the increased focus on sugarcane cultivation has also raised concerns regarding soil degradation, water usage, and crop diversity.

This study aims to explore the multifaceted impact of sugar factories on agricultural development in Karad Tahsil, highlighting their role in improving rural livelihoods while addressing the challenges posed to sustainable agricultural practices.

Changing Cropping Pattern:

The proportion of area under different crops at a given period in the study region is revealed by a study of shifting cropping patterns. Cropping patterns in the study area are constantly changing due to price fluctuations in agricultural products, government policies, and other physical and non-physical factors. Cropping patterns are influenced by economic, social, and personal variables and environmental elements such as physiographic and meteorological circumstances. The average area under various crops and the relative percentage of each crop in the gross cultivated area has been calculated in the study region.

Cropping Pattern In Karad Tahsil:

For the entire Karad Tahsil, the changing cropping pattern is investigated. More than grain crops, the pattern of cash crops and orchards has altered. The proportion of land planted in cereal crops has decreased. About 85 percent of the land was planted with cereal crops during the investigation period, compared to roughly 65 percent. Sugarcane, Soyabean, Groundnut, and Pulses have seen an increase in area under cultivation, whilst Bajara and Maize have seen a significant decrease in area under cultivation. The changes in the Karad Tahsil are clearly shown in table 3.8. The entire Tahsil's cropping pattern has been studied.

Concept of Development in Geography:

Development is a term that is both region and time-specific. It implies that the definition of development can differ from one area to the next, as well as from one time to the next within the same area. Given that different social sciences have their viewpoints on development due to differences in theory, geographers' new view provides the most comprehensive conceptualization of the development process.

Various disciplines, such as economics, sociology, politics, research,

history, and geography, often deal with the growth process from their perspective. They have their understanding of the creation process, which is in line with the thrust and theory of their respective disciplines. However, among the different social sciences, economics surpasses the contributions of other social scientists. Economists have expressed their views on development in terms of economic growth when it comes to conceptualizing development and formulating development models and theories.

Study Region:

Karad tahsil lies in the Satara district of Maharashtra, India, consisting of 216 villages. Geographically Karad tahsil is located between 1706't 74032' North Latitude and 730 58' to 740 16' East Longitude. It has an average elevation of 566 meters. It lies at the confluence of the Krishna and Koyana Rivers, called 'Preeti Sangam,' meaning the confluence of love. It has a maximum temperature of 410 oC and a minimum of 150 oC. The average annual rainfall in Karad is 700 mm and has a total area of 566 m2. It is located in a hilly region. The Krishna, Koyana, Uttar mand, Tarali, and their tributaries have well-developed drainage patterns in the study area.

Karad tahsil has a population of 1630272 people, according to the 2011 census. The sex ratio in Karad tahsil is 972 females per 1000 males, with a literacy rate of 75.54 percent. Basalt is the main stone in this region, with distinctive black soil occupying the river valley. The Deccan trap is the only geological formation in this area. In this region, agriculture is the major occupation.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the variable for the agriculture development in Karad Tahsil.
2. To study the impact of sugar factory on Agriculture Development in karad Tahsil.

Research Methodology:

Bhatia's location quotient method of crop concentration is the greatest way to measure spatial distinction in Karad Tahsil's cropping pattern. Eleven major crops, including jowar, bajara, maize, wheat, pulses, sugarcane, fruits, oilseeds, rice, spices, and fibers, were analyzed and measured in the Karad Tahsil.

For the calculation of the location quotient, Bhatia's approach is employed. The

Table: Crop Concentration Calculated by Bhatia's Method in Karad Tahsil

CROPS	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2000-01	2010-11	2018-19
Rice	2.75	1.57	1.90	1.47	1.48	1.49	0.25
Wheat	1.02	0.51	0.58	0.93	1.23	1.17	0.27
Jowar	8.20	1.00	0.91	0.28	1.24	0.93	0.50
Bajara	0.02	0.10	0.02	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.00
Maize	3.61	2.83	1.25	2.15	4.00	0.39	0.51
Total Pulses	5.93	0.67	0.54	0.38	0.39	0.66	0.10
Sugarcane	2.57	3.20	3.52	3.46	3.33	4.32	2.83
Spices	2.54	2.15	1.79	0.94	0.66	0.57	1.52
fruits and vegetables	0.58	0.51	0.79	0.56	0.47	0.61	1.76
total fibers	0.48	0.24	0.25	1.96	0.47	0.41	0.84
total oilseeds	2.11	2.05	1.89	2.52	2.02	1.47	1.34

Source: Calculated by a researcher

crop concentration in Karad Tahsil is calculated using the formula below.

Index for determining the concentration of crop 'a'

$$= \frac{\text{area of crop 'a' area unit}}{\text{Total Cropped}} \times \frac{\text{Area of crop 'a' in the entire region}}{\text{Area of all crops entire region}}$$

There have been significant variations in the area patterns of the crop concentration in the study region.

Crop Concentration in Karad Tahsil:

Crop density variation in a specific area or region at any given moment is referred to as crop concentration. Physiographic, climatic, hydrological, socio-economic, and technological elements that affect crop concentration define the spatial variance in crop density. The location measurement approach is often employed for crop concentration analysis. Many geographers have used this method to estimate the density of individual crops. Geographers such as Florence (1948), Chisholm (1962), Bhatia (1965), and Jasbir Singh (1976) contributed to the use of the quotient method to mark the agricultural zone. Using the quotient approach, Florence (1948) compared a region's contribution to that of the entire country. With the use of the coefficient of localization, Chisholm (1962) attempted to use a quotient to measure the relative regional concentration.

1. 1960-61:

All crop concentrations in the Karad Tahsil are shown in Table 4.4. As can be seen from the table above, jowar and total pulses crops had a high level of crop concentration in 1960-61.

Because irrigation facilities were not built at the time, and a sugar mill had not been constructed, people's attitudes toward agriculture were based solely on substances. Rice, maize, sugar cane, spice, and oilseed crops are all at a medium degree of concentration this year (4-2).

Because of the unfavorable conditions for Bajara crops and fiber crops in Karad, Bajra, fruits and vegetables and fiber crops have a very low crop concentration. The wheat crop is merely sufficient to meet the demands of the household.

2. 1970-71:

Sugarcane crop had the highest level of crop concentration in this decade, as shown in the table above. Sugarcane is the highest level of crop concentration, so the Krishna sugar factory constructed and developed the irrigation facility in 1961. Maize, spices, and oil seeds follow sugarcane. Crop concentration is reported to be moderate. Rice, wheat, bajara, total pulses, fruits and vegetables, and total fiber are all found in relatively low concentrations in this decade.

3. 1980-81:

The total crop concentration in the Karad Tahsil is shown in Table 4.4. The accompanying Table showed a very high concentration of sugar cane crop in 1980-81 (3.52); because a second factory was being built in the study area at this time. Rice, spices, and total oilseed crops have a medium crop concentration. Sugarcane intercropping oil seeds are discovered in the research area. Wheat, jowar, bajara, fruits and vegetables, and fiber crops have very low crop concentrations.

4. 1990-91:

Sugarcane crop had the highest level of crop concentration in this decade, as

shown in the table above. Crop concentration is reported to be moderate. Crops of maize and total oilseeds maize are used as animal feed and a food crop in the research area. Wheat, jowar, bajara, pulses, spices, fibers, and fruits and vegetables crop concentrations have been determined to be very low in this decade.

5. 2000-01:

As shown in Table 4.4, in the Karad Tahsil, a very high-level crop concentration is maize and sugarcane. Sugar cane is the dominant crop in the study region. But maize is mostly intercropping crop in the Karad Tahsil. Mainly Small-scale factories depend on Maize crops. In the Karad tahsil, the medium level of crop concentration is oilseeds. In oilseeds, soybean and groundnut are the most dominant oilseeds crops. Very low crop concentration is found in food crops, spices, fibers and fruit vegetables. This is because these crops are cultivated only to meet their needs.

6. 2010-11:

The crop concentrations in the research area are shown in Table 4.4. Sugarcane was the dominating crop from 2001 to 2010, with very high levels of crop concentration. (4.32).

Many sugar factory irrigation facilities were installed after independence until 2010-11. Compared to other Tahsils in the Satara district, the Karad Tahsil sugarcane crop has a high concentration.

Another crop is a very low-level concentrate food crop, pulses, oilseeds, spices, and fruit and vegetables with very low-level concentration found in the decade 2000-01 to 2010.

7. 2018-19:

Sugarcane has likewise been a high-level crop focus in this decade. Sugarcane is the only crop that concentrates at a very high level compared to other crops.

**Agricultural
Characteristics:**

In rural India, agriculture is a significant sector. This sector directly

Development

employs over 65 percent of the population. Farmers are continually looking for ways to increase their farm's profitability. Farmers will develop their farms if they make more money, but if they grow grain crops, they will not make as much money as if they grow a cash crop like sugarcane. Farmers' profits are reduced due to inappropriate farming methods, aged seeds, irrational fertilizer and pesticide use, lack of agriculture knowledge, and insufficient water availability, among other factors. Sugar factories create a single agricultural development section that takes into account all of these disadvantages. This section offers advice to farmers on improving the quality and quantity of their crops using current and scientific agricultural methods. In this approach, industries take extraordinary steps to help rural farmers.

This section's primary goal is to expand the area under sugarcane cultivation. In the Tahsil of Karad, there are four sugar factories in operation. Two sugar factories operate in the co-operative sector, while the other operates in the private sector. Both enterprises are attempting to ameliorate the situation in the agricultural sector. A few indications clearly illustrate the progress made in the Karad Tahsil.

Irrigated farming and rainfed farming in Karad Tahsil:

Irrigated farming is the predominant type of agriculture in Karad Tahsil, as it is in the Satara district (Bagayati farming). Irrigated farming is a method of farming practiced in areas with an annual rainfall of 200 cm and well-developed irrigation facilities. In a year, there are two main agricultural seasons. The summer season is known as Kharif, and the winter season is known as Rabi. The Kharif season begins in June with the arrival of the south-west monsoon, with seeds being planted in June and July and harvesting in September and October. During the Kharif season, crops that require a lot of water are grown. The rabi season begins in the middle of October when the south-east monsoon arrives. In October, seeds are planted, and harvests are harvested in March and April. During the rabi season, crops that require less water are typically planted. Jowar is the most common rabi crop. Aside from the aforementioned crops, irrigated crops, also known as Bagayati crops, are farmed all year under irrigation. Sugarcane and soybean are the principal crops irrigated artificially in Karad Tahsil. The percentage of farmers in Karad Tahsil who practice two forms of agriculture is shown in table 4.5.

Table: Types of Farming method in Karad Tahsil

Sr.no	Types of Agriculture	Before sugar Factory	Percentage	After sugar Factory	Percentage
1	Irrigated farming	375	41.66	670	74.44
2	Rainfed farming	525	58.33	230	25.55
	Total	900	100	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-20).

The sugar factory irrigation scheme, Krishna canal, Gokak scheme, Yevati Dam, and irrigation facilities made accessible to farmers have radically changed the nature of agriculture in the Karad Tahsil, as shown in Table 4.5. As a result, 41.66 percent of farmers practiced irrigated farming before the sugar Factory, while 58.33 percent practiced non-irrigated farming.

With the growth of the sugar business and the development of irrigation systems, the nature of agriculture has radically altered. Irrigated farming is practiced by over 74.44 percent of farmers, while non-irrigated farming is practiced by only 25 percent of farmers.

Farming instruments:

Various types of implements were utilized for agricultural operations between 1960 and 2018, and some of them are

addressed here as the study's reference period. The cultivation of crops necessitates the use of tools. It is difficult to cultivate

without using wooden and iron farming implements. Both of these instruments are powered by animals.

Table: Use of farming instruments in agriculture

Sr.no	Types of instrument	Before Sugar Factory	Percentage	After sugar Factory	Percentage
1	Wooden	706	78.44	308	34.22
2	Iron	194	21.56	592	65.78
	Total	900	100	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-20).

A typical implement is a wooden plow, which farmers commonly use. Prior to 1960, food grain production was significant in Karad Tahsil. Farmers in Karad Tahsil were seen utilizing the most wood implements prior to 1970. Farmers employed them in 78.44 percent of cases, despite this region's invention of iron plugs. Iron plugs were not available to everyone even before independence.

In 2018, however, a new sugar factory was established in Karad Tahsil. The sugar factory's economic development goes hand in hand with its development. Farmers'

economic development in Karad Tahsil has improved.

Means of tillages:

Agricultural progress relies on advanced agricultural technology (Kanawade M.C., 1984). Tractors are utilized in some regions for plowing, and oxen are used in others to cultivate the land. Cultivating oxen takes a long time and requires much effort, whereas farming with tractors takes less time and effort. The growth of sugar factories in Karad Tahsil reflects the farmers' economic progress. As a result, farmers choose to cultivate with tractors rather than oxen.

Table: Karad Tahsil: Means of Tillage

Sr. No	Means of Tillage	Before sugar Factory	Percentage	After sugar Factory	Percentage
1	With the help of oxen pair	560	60	314	34.88
2	With the help of a tractor	340	40	586	65.11
	Total	900	100.00	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-20).

The above table demonstrates that before the sugar factory, a large percentage of farmers were involved in oxen farming. Farmers engaged in oxen farming accounted for 60 percent of all farmers, whereas tractor farming accounted for 40 percent of all farmers.

The above table illustrates that after the sugar factory, due to the economic development of sugar factories or the economic well-being of farmers, the rate of cultivation with oxen has declined, as it

takes more time and personnel to cultivate with oxen. The number of oxen farmers has decreased to 34.8 percent. The percentage of farmers who use tractors has risen to 65.11 percent.

Trend of growth in the number of tractors:

The study of growth in the number of tractors in the study area is essential. An attempt has been made to trace the number of tractors in Karad Tahsil.

Table : Decadal Growth in the Number of Tractors In Karad Tahsil (Year 1971 to 2011)

Sr. No.	Tahsil	1971	1981	1991	2001	2011
1	Karad	201	416	907	1460	5200

Source: Records of RTO Office Karad Tahsil (Vijaynagar)

The above table depicts the increase in tractors in Karad Tahsil. In the year 1971, the Karad Tahsil had 201 tractors. The distribution differs from one village to the next. In 1971, Karad Tahsil ranked first in the Satara district with 201 tractors. The tractors climbed to 416 in the

Methods of sugarcane cutting:

Table: Methods of sugarcane cutting

Sr. No	Method of Sugarcane Cutting	Count	Percentage
1	Humans	586	65.11
2	Instruments	314	34.89
Total		900	100.00

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

When the cane is ripe, it must be gathered by a man or a cane harvester before being delivered to the factory. Karad tahsil has a significant region covered in cane. According to Table 4.9, human labor accounts for 65.18 percent of cane harvesting in Karad tahsil, while machine labor accounts for 34.89 percent.

Changes in Source of Irrigation:

"Irrigation," according to Cantor (1967), is the artificial application of water to the soil for agricultural production. Irrigation is a civilization-old art form. Irrigation water from various sources is applied to the land in a variety of ways, depending on the slope of the field, the kind of soil, and the crop to be lifted. In this regard, data is gathered through distributing questionnaires to sample communities and reinforced by frequent field visits.

Irrigation in the study region began with the opening of the Krishna Canal during the early time of the British administration. Still, the whole building of the rapid began in 1864 and was finished in 1867. They were 60.66 meters long and 7.0 meters tall and were located near Khodashi in Karad Tahsil, across the Krishna. The Krishna canal distributes 160.06 cubic meters of water every second, irrigating

following decade, from 1980 to 1981. The year 2011 was distinguished by significant growth in tractors, which reached 5200 units. The significant development of agro-based sectors and the favorable influence of co-operative sugar factories.

3,079.02 hectares of cultivable land. Prior to this project, the primary irrigation source was mainly wells, and water was lifted using a lift and a water wheel. State and federal governments have started many more irrigation projects to bring a total of 123 acres under irrigation by supplying water through canals and other irrigation sources. Many co-operative societies in the Satara district have developed and built a dense network of lift, drip, and sprinkler irrigation due to government policies encouraging the use of surface and groundwater resources through financial help and subsidies.

Methods of irrigation:

Irrigation is an essential input in agriculture and one of the most significant components of agricultural technology for increasing agricultural productivity. Because sugarcane is a perennial crop, it requires a massive amount of water. As a result, the area under sugarcane has risen due to the creation of sugar factories. As a result, sugar mills assist farmers in constructing various irrigation sources and irrigation plans, among other things. Various types of irrigation sources created and used by farmers in Karad Tahsil are shown in Table 4.10.

Table: Sources of Irrigation

Sr. No	Irrigation Methods	Before sugar Factory		After sugar Factory	
		No of Respondents	Percentage	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Canal	76	8.44	95	10.55
2	Boar Well	35	3.88	175	19.44
3	Well	275	30.55	190	21.11
4	Lift Irrigation	39	4.33	395	43.88
5	Dep On Rainfall	475	52.77	45	5
Grand Total		900	100	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

Table 4.13 reveals that, before 2001, 52.77 percent of farmers relied on rainfall as their primary supply of water for irrigation. Extensive irrigation is well developed in the southern section of Karad Tahsil, with 30.55 percent of farmers using it. Canal irrigation is used by 8.44 percent of farmers, whereas lift irrigation is used by 4.33 percent.

After the development of sugar factories in 2001, which aided the development of lift irrigation schemes, 43.88 percent of farmers now rely on lift irrigation. Farmers primarily use lift irrigation facilities in Karad Tahsil. Boar well irrigation is used

by 19.44 percent of farms, whereas well irrigation is used by 21.11 percent. The eastern section of Karad Tahsil is now accessible thanks to the completion of the Krishna canal on the Krishna River.

➤ **Types of irrigation systems:**

There are many different irrigation systems, depending on how the water is distributed throughout the field. Surface irrigation, Localized irrigation, Drip irrigation, Sprinkler irrigation, Center pivot irrigation, Lateral move irrigation, Manual irrigation, etc., are the types of irrigation systems. Some common irrigation systems include Traditional, Drip, Sprinkler, etc.

Table: Irrigation Systems in Karad Tahsil

Sr. No	Irrigation Systems	No. of farmers	Percentage
1.	Traditional	554	61.55
2	'Drip	238	26.44
3	Sprinkler	49	5.44
4	Other	59	6.55
Grand Total		900	100.00

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

It was critical to analyze the technology of irrigation agriculture when considering the agriculture of Karad Tahsil and its aftermath. When farmers in Karad Tahsil were questioned, it was discovered that traditional irrigation methods were being used more and more. Surface irrigation, targeted irrigation, manual irrigation, and insistence irrigation are all examples of traditional irrigation techniques. Traditional farming methods were found to be used by 61.55 percent of farmers. Drip and sprinkler irrigation systems haven't been

developed extensively in Karad Tahsil because irrigation water isn't a big concern. Drip irrigation was found to be used by 26.44 percent of farmers, whereas sprinkler irrigation was used by 5.44 percent of farmers. Other irrigation systems were seen being used by some farmers.

Types of Fertilizers:

Fertilizers are routinely used to grow all crops, with treatment rates varying depending on soil fertility, which is usually determined by a soil test and crop type. Sugarcane growth is reliant on the

availability of essential nutrients. Even if the soil is capable of natural regeneration, it is unable to offer all of those nutrients on its own. It is required to feed the additional nutrients in order to meet all of the key plant nutrient requirements. Fertilizer has a long-term impact on agricultural growth and is a critical component of agricultural development. Fertilizer application has an essential function in crop yield. There are two types of fertilizers that are used to boost crop output. Sugarcane, for example, necessitates a greater amount of fertilizer. Sugarcane sugar is the most important component. Sugar is a chemical compound made up of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen found in sugarcane. None of them is derived from the soil.

It is critical that these components develop properly and are preserved.

Sugarcane, for example, necessitates a large amount of fertilizer. Inorganic fertilizers are widely utilized all over the world. This is because the consequences are immediate. Organic fertilizers also increase sugarcane output, but they work much more slowly than inorganic fertilizers. Various fertilizers such as DAP, Urea, 10-26-26, 18-46, 10-15-15, and Superphosphate are commonly used for sugarcane crops. Organic fertilizers are also popular, although they are difficult to come by and are also highly expensive. Compost, cow manure, Neem fertilizers, and poultry waste are some of the most well-known organic fertilizers. And those are both beneficial to enhancing productivity and protecting soil health. Table 4.12 shows the types of fertilizers used by sugarcane producers in the Karad Tahsil before and after 2001.

Table: Fertilizers used by farmers in Karad Tahsil

Sr. No	Type of Fertilizers	Before Factory		After Factory	
		No of Respondents	Percentage	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Organic chemical	132	14.66	401	44.55
2	Chemical	21	2.34	401	44.55
3	Organic	747	83	98	10.90
Grand Total		900	100	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

According to the table above, 14.66 percent of farmers employ organic and chemical fertilizers before the Sugar Factory. Chemical fertilizers are used by 2.34 percent of farmers. Organic fertilizers are used by 83 percent of farmers.

Farmers in this region were not economically established prior to the sugar business, so more farmers emphasized using organic fertilizers. However, the scenario today, or after 2001, is radically different.

Table 4.12 shows that 44.55 percent of farmers employ organic and chemical fertilizers after the Sugar Factory. 10.90 percent of farmers use organic fertilizers. Chemical fertilizers are used by 44.55 percent of farmers.

Sugar cane varieties:

The study region pilot seed plots are planted with a variety of sugarcane cultivars. Sugarcane seed of the highest quality is the foundation of high-yielding sugarcane. As a result, choosing the right cane seed is crucial. There are a variety of cane varieties accessible right now. Co-671, Co-265, Co-92061, Co-86032, Co-8021, Co-8014, and Co-100001 are important once again. All of these truths are true in practice. Cultivation is done with Co-671, Co-86032, and Co-265.

After 10 to 10 months, the early growth of types is available for harvesting. Early varieties are often planted early in the implant season and crushed in the early part of the crushing season. These cultivars can produce up to 100 to 120 tonnes per hectare. At 12 to 14 months, mid-late maturing

varieties are ready for harvesting. Co-7219, Co-86032, Co-6304, Co-8021, and Co-8014 are the codes. These are typically high-yielding varieties with a moderate sugar recovery rate. The Co- 86032 variety may be found in most sugarcane-growing areas. It yields 110 to 125 tonnes per hectare in Karad Tahsil.

Late-growing cultivars are ready to harvest at the age of 14 to 16 months. Co-62125 and Co-86032 are the codes. In the Karad Tahsil, Co-94012 is a popular variety. The sugarcane variety was created and promoted by the central sugarcane research

institute in Coimbatore. As a result, CO is used to name these properties (Coimbatore).

Cane seeds that are good for you have certain qualities. Only seeds that have been in the ground for at least 10 to 11 months and are still immature with a lot of juice and green buds are acceptable. Plantation of cane seeds with three, two, or one buddings can be done for the sake of ensuring healthy growth and maximum productivity. As a result, sugarcane seeds of this quality are highly sought (Deshmukh S.B., 1983). The sugarcane types grown in Karad Tahsil are the following (Table 4.13).

Table: Karad Tahsil: Sugarcane Varieties

Sr. no.	Verities of sugarcane	No. of farmers	Percentage
1	CO- 671 AND CO-265	180	20
2	CO-265 AND CO- 86032	210	23.33
3	CO- 86032	480	53.33
4	CO- 94012, CO- 671, CO- 8001	30	3.33
Total		900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork, 2019-20

According to table 4.13, around 53.33 percent of farmers favor the co-86032 sugarcane variety. About 23.33 percent of farmers used sugarcane varieties co-617 and co-265, whereas 20 percent preferred sugarcane varieties co-265 and co-671. According to their experience, just 3.33

percent of farmers favor the co-94012, co-671, and co-8001 sorts of varieties.

Sugarcane Total Farm:

In the Tahsil, the number of sugar factories has expanded, as has the number of irrigation facilities for sugarcane. The area under sugarcane in Karad Tahsil is shown in Table 4.14.

Table: Sugarcane total farmland in farmers of Karad Tahsil

Sr. No	Sugarcane Total farm (In Acre)	Before sugar Factory		After sugar Factory	
		No of Respondents	Percentage	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	0_1	718	79.78	180	20
2	1_2	14	1.56	202	22.44
3	2_3	99	11	175	19.44
4	3_4	22	2.44	112	12.44
5	4_5	18	2	49	5.44
6	5_6	29	3.22	26	2.89
7	6_7	0	0	15	1.67
8	7_8	0	0	30	3.33
9	8_9	0	0	22	2.44
10	9_10	0	0	39	4.33
11	10+	0	0	40	4.44
Grand Total		900	100	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

According to the table above, approximately 79.78 percent of people have five acres of land under sugarcane cultivation prior to the Sugar Factory.

Farmers in Karad Tahsil used to grow crops other than sugarcane before the sugar business. As a result, the area under sugarcane is smaller. Only 1.56 percent of

farmers had two acres of sugarcane farmland. According to the findings, farmers were not planting sugarcane on around 6 acres of land.

Sugarcane area will be increased due to the development of several irrigation transportation infrastructures following the Sugar Factory. Following the Sugar Factory, it was discovered that 20 percent of farmers have 1 acre of land dedicated to sugarcane growing. Farmers with two acres of sugarcane land account for 22.74 percent of the total. Only 4.44 percent of farmers have more than ten acres of sugarcane growing area, and 19.44 percent have three acres.

Size of landholding:

Table: Landholding size

Sr. No.	Nature of Landholding	No. of Framer	Percentage
1	Small farmers (Below 5 acres)	560	62.22
2	Medium farmers (5 to 10 acres)	220	24.44
3	Big farmers (Above 10 acres)	120	13.33
	Total	900	100

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

Table 4.21 reveals that small farmers account for 62.22 percent of farmers in Karad Tahsil with less than five acres of land, medium farmers account for 24.44 percent of farmers with five to ten acres of land, and large farmers account for 13.33 percent of farmers with more than ten acres of land.

Intercropping in sugarcane:

With its Adsali and pre-season planting strategy, sugarcane is a long-term crop. This crop has been on the fields for a long time. Sugarcane seeds require roughly

Landholding size plays an essential role in the growth of agriculture, particularly in the modernization and commercialization of agriculture. Traditionally, Karad Tahsil was an irrigated area. However, with the building of the sugar plant, irrigation conveyance has improved, cropping patterns have altered, sugar cane cultivation has grown, and agricultural mechanization and commercialization have advanced in the region. However, the bulk of farmers continues to employ traditional methods and equipment in agricultural activities because mechanization is not feasible for them due to their modest landholding size. Table 4.19 shows the size of land holdings in the Karad Tahsil.

six to eight weeks sprouting, followed by a six-week filling time before entering the most recent grand phase of growth. When it only begins to grow eagerly and covers the ground. It is feasible to take intercrop during this time, which might finish its life cycle in three to four months. Intercropping like this is more cost-effective than growing sugarcane alone. Sugar mills are encouraging farmers to engage in such intercropping. Farmers in Karad Tahsil are intercropping, as seen in Table 4.16.

Table: Karad Tahsil: Inter cropping in sugarcane Karad Tahsil

Sr. No	Crops Other Than Sugarcane	No, of farmers	Percentage
1	Maize,	24	2.66
2	Pulses	74	8.22
3	Groundnut	320	35.55
4	Soybean	224	24.88
5	Onion	47	5.22
6	Leafy Vegetables	25	2.77
7	No intercropping	186	20.66
	Total	900	100

Table 4.20 reveals that approximately 75 percent of sugarcane farmers engage in intercropping. 2.66 percent of these people prefer maize as an intercropping crop. Maize is used as animal fodder by farmers. Around 35 percent of farmers prefer groundnut as an intercropping crop, whereas 24.88 percent prefer soybean. However, around 20 percent of farmers still plant a single sugarcane crop.

Sugarcane Plantation:

Sugarcane plantations differ from one region to the next. The geographical attribute distinguishes the area in the research region, and sugarcane plantations vary. There are two sorts of plantations. There are two types of plantations: wet and dry. The wet plantation is carried out in light and medium soil types. The line is flooded, and the can sticks are shoved 3 to 6 cm into the soil to keep the buds up. The dry planting is done on high-yielding black soil.

Dry earth is used to press the can sticks. The buds are placed on a sod, covered with soil, and watered.

I] Planting season for sugarcane:

The climate is conducive to sugarcane production. It takes roughly six to eight weeks for sugarcane to mature. Following that, it takes four to six weeks to file, after which it enters the early noble period of growth. It swiftly grows and sheds the earth ultimately. The length of the growing season is determined by the season of agriculture. In Maharashtra, there are four seasons for farming and growing. The Adsali sugarcane seeds take roughly 16 to 18 months to mature. The Adsali orchard is usually used from the end of June until August. Adsali has a good yield per acre. The sugarcane crop before the season, but not as much as adsali. Suru, a seasonal crop, takes roughly a year to mature. In December and January, the orchard is finished.

Table:Period of sugarcane plantation in Karad Tahsil

Sr. No	Period of sugarcane plantation	Count	Percentage
1	Adsali	570.00	63.33
2	Adsali, Suruchi	224.00	24.89
3	Suruchi	106.00	11.78
Grand Total		900.00	100.00

Source: Based on fieldwork (2019-2020)

The Adasali plantation is mostly done in the rainy season, from late June to August. Its growth and maturity are dependent on the passage of 16 to 18 months. As a result, the Adsali sugarcane crop will be in the fold until the next rainy season. Harvesting begins in October and November, followed by the winter, which aids in its growth. Irrigation facilities are required to be more intermediate in the summer. Summer is followed by the rainy season, and ranching begins after the rainy season. As a result, Adsali has a high yield per hectare, and around 63 percent of farmers in Karad Tahsil favor Adsali cultivation.

Suruchi plantation takes place primarily throughout November and December. It takes about a year for it to mature. This Suruchi plantation goes

through two winter and two summer seasons before being harvested. Because the majority of the harvesting takes place in March and April. Suru plantation has a lower yield per hectare than other plantations, and only 12 percent of farmers in Karad Tahsil chose Suruchi planting. These sorts of cane planting procedures are utilized by farmers that have a considerable amount of land. Only 25 percent of farmers in Karad Tahsil choose both plantations.

Conclusions:

1. Growth of the sugar business and the development of irrigation systems, the nature of agriculture has radically altered. Irrigated farming is practiced by over 74.44 percent of farmers, while non-irrigated farming is

- practiced by only 25 percent of farmers.
2. A typical implement is a wooden plow, which farmers commonly use. Prior to 1960, food grain production was significant in Karad Tahsil. Farmers in Karad Tahsil were seen utilizing the most wood implements prior to 1970. Farmers employed them in 78.44 percent of cases, despite this region's invention of iron plugs. Iron plugs were not available to everyone even before independence.
 3. Demonstrates that before the sugar factory, a large percentage of farmers were involved in oxen farming. Farmers engaged in oxen farming accounted for 60 percent of all farmers, whereas tractor farming accounted for 40 percent of all farmers.
 4. Illustrates that after the sugar factory, due to the economic development of sugar factories or the economic well-being of farmers, the rate of cultivation with oxen has declined, as it takes more time and personnel to cultivate with oxen. The number of oxen farmers has decreased to 34.8 percent. The percentage of farmers who use tractors has risen to 65.11 percent.
 5. Human labor accounts for 65.18 percent of cane harvesting in Karad tahsil, while machine labor accounts for 34.89 percent.
 6. Extensive irrigation is well developed in the southern section of Karad Tahsil, with 30.55 percent of farmers using it. Canal irrigation is used by 8.44 percent of farmers, whereas lift irrigation is used by 4.33 percent.
 7. Traditional farming methods were found to be used by 61.55 percent of farmers. Drip and sprinkler irrigation systems haven't been developed extensively in Karad Tahsil because irrigation water isn't a big concern.
- Drip irrigation was found to be used by 26.44 percent of farmers, whereas sprinkler irrigation was used by 5.44 percent of farmers. Other irrigation systems were seen being used by some farmers.
8. 14.66 percent of farmers employ organic and chemical fertilizers before the Sugar Factory. Chemical fertilizers are used by 2.34 percent of farmers. Organic fertilizers are used by 83 percent of farmers.
 9. 44.55 percent of farmers employ organic and chemical fertilizers after the Sugar Factory. 10.90 percent of farmers use organic fertilizers. Chemical fertilizers are used by 44.55 percent of farmers.
 10. 53.33 percent of farmers favor the co-86032 sugarcane variety. About 23.33 percent of farmers used sugarcane varieties co-617 and co-265, whereas 20 percent preferred sugarcane varieties co-265 and co-671. According to their experience, just 3.33 percent of farmers favor the co-94012, co-671, and co-8001 sorts of varieties.
 11. Small farmers account for 62.22 percent of farmers in Karad Tahsil with less than five acres of land, medium farmers account for 24.44 percent of farmers with five to ten acres of land, and large farmers account for 13.33 percent of farmers with more than ten acres of land.
 12. 75 percent of sugarcane farmers engage in intercropping. 2.66 percent of these people prefer maize as an intercropping crop. Maize is used as animal fodder by farmers. Around 35 percent of farmers prefer groundnut as an intercropping crop, whereas 24.88 percent prefer soybean. However, around 20 percent of farmers still plant a single sugarcane crop.

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